

VITAMIN D AND PARKINSON'S DISEASE

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Vitamin D is suggested to play an important role in neurodegenerative disorders.

Objective

To examine the association between serum 25 vitamin D3 and Parkinson's disease (PD).

Materials and methods

Fifty patients suffering from PD and fifty age- and sex-matched healthy control subjects were included in the study. Patients were subjected to complete clinical assessment, and Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS) was done to evaluate severity of PD. Measurement of serum 25 vitamin D3 using enzyme-linked immuno sorbent assay (ELISA) was done for both patients and controls.

Results

Serum 25 vitamin D3 was significantly lower in PD patients compared to healthy controls. Twenty-five vitamin D3 serum level was significantly negatively correlated with age and age at onset of disease but not significantly correlated with disease duration and severity of Parkinson's disease. Multiple regression analysis showed that serum 25 vitamin D3 was not found to be predictor for severity of PD.

Conclusion

There is an association between low vitamin D levels and PD. Therefore, vitamin D may have a role in the pathophysiology of PD.

Keywords: Vitamin D, Parkinson's disease, degeneration, neurology.

Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is the second most common neurodegenerative disorder after Alzheimer's disease in the elderly. Pathologically, there is a slow and progressive degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra, although its etiology is not fully understood (1).

Vitamin D is an environmentally modifiable factor as it is largely determined by diet and sunlight exposure. The enzyme 1-alpha hydroxylase converts the stored 25 hydroxyvitamin D form to the biologically active vitamin D form 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3 which then binds to vitamin D receptor (VDR) (2).

Vitamin D was proposed to alter cholinergic, dopaminergic, and noradrenergic neurotransmitter pathways in the central nervous system (CNS). It has been demonstrated that vitamin D plays a role in dopamine synthesis through regulation of tyrosine hydroxylase gene (3).

Vitamin D has been implicated in PD through its effects on L-type voltage-sensitive calcium channels (L-VSCC), nerve growth factor (NGF), matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), prostaglandins (PGs) and cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), reactive oxygen species (ROS), and nitric oxide synthase (NOS) (4).

Previous studies have reported an association between PD and serum vitamin D, but the results are controversial (5).

The present study aimed to assess serum 25 vitamin D3 status in PD patients and its relation to clinical parameters and disease severity.

Materials and methods

This case control study was carried on hundred subjects (50 patients diagnosed as PD and 50 age and gender healthy matched subjects).

Patients were selected from the Neurology outpatient clinic and Neurology department of Cairo University Hospitals. Control subjects were recruited from relatives of hospitalized patients in the Neurology department. The aim and procedures of the study were explained to every participant, and an informed consent was obtained before being enrolled in the study. The study was approved by the ethical committee of department of Neurology, Faculty of medicine, Cairo University Hospitals.

Included in this study are patients (of both sexes) fulfilling the criteria for diagnosis of idiopathic Parkinson's disease according to the British Brain Bank criteria (6). Their age ranged from 45–70 (to minimize the effect of aging on vitamin D level).

Excluded from this study are patients with concomitant medical illness (Diabetes Mellitus, hepatic and renal diseases); patients with MRI brain showing structural lesions; patients having bone diseases or receiving drugs that may affect bone health as corticoster-

oids, antidepressant, anxiolytics, proton pump inhibitors, H₂ receptor blockers or chemotherapeutic agents, and patients taking vitamin D supplements; and patients receiving drugs that may interact with serum vitamin D level as antiepileptic drugs, diuretics, and anti-coagulants.

Methods

Patients were submitted to thorough neurological examination and assessment and staging of PD using Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS). Serum level of 25 vitamin D was measured for patients and controls using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) technique. Venous blood samples were collected then centrifuged to get serum. The KIA kit was used for the quantitative measurement of total 25-OH vitamin D₃ in serum using the competitive immunoassay technique.

Statistical methods

Data were coded and entered using the statistical package SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 25. Data was summarized using mean, standard deviation, median, minimum, and maximum in quantitative data and using frequency (count) and relative frequency (percentage) for categorical data. Comparisons between quantitative variables were done using the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney tests. For comparing categorical data, Chi-square test was performed. Exact test was used when the expected frequency is less than 5. Correlations between quantitative variables were done using Spearman's correlation coefficient. Linear regression analysis was done to predict total severity scores using vitamin D. Logistic regression was done to detect independent predictors of severity. P values less than 0.05 were considered as statistically significant.

Results

The age of patients ranged from 47–70 years with a mean age 60.78 ± 5.10 years. The age of control subjects ranged from 45–70 years with a mean age 61.30 ± 5.61 years. The patients group included 32 male (64%) and 18 female (36%). The control group included 30 male (60%) and 20 female (40%). Patients and controls were matched regarding mean age and sex distribution ($p = 0.545$ and 0.680 respectively).

In the patient group, the mean serum level of 25 vitamin D₃ was 6.10 ± 2.55 ng/ml. Serum 25 vitamin D₃ was deficient in 45 patients (90%) and insufficient in 5 patients (10%). In the control group, the mean serum level of 25 vitamin D₃ was 7.46 ± 3.61 ng/ml. Serum vitamin D was optimum in 1 subject (2%), insufficient in 9 subjects (18%), and deficient in 40 subjects (80%).

Mean serum vitamin D₃ level was significantly lower in PD patients compared to healthy controls ($P = 0.029$).

No significant difference was found between disease stages as regards mean age, age at onset, or serum 25 vitamin D₃ level ($p = 0.456$, 0.189 , and 0.372 respectively).

Serum 25 vitamin D₃ level was significantly negatively correlated with age and age at onset of disease ($p = 0.015$, $r = -0.34$), ($p = 0.038$, $r = -0.29$) respectively. However, serum 25 vitamin D₃ level was not significantly correlated with disease duration, UPDRS scores, and modified H and Y staging.

Linear regression analysis was done between total scores of mentation, activity of daily living, and motor examination as dependent factors and serum 25 vitamin D₃ as independent factor. Logistic regression analysis was also done between modified H and Y scale as dependent factor and serum vitamin D₃ as independent factor. The P value was not significant after adjustment for age, sex, age at onset of disease, and disease duration. This indicates that serum 25 vitamin D₃ is not an independent predictor for both UPDRS scores and H and Y staging.

Conclusion

With the limitations of this study, it could be concluded that there is an association between low vitamin D levels and PD. Future studies are recommended to clarify the possible role of vitamin D in the pathogenesis, progression, and severity of the disease.

References

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